

Microdetermination of palladium using benzildioxime and thiocyanate

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Abstract : Palladium(II) forms a light yellow 1 : 1 : 2 complex with benzildioxime in presence of thiocyanate at 0.10–1.00 mol L⁻¹ HCl. The complex is non-extractable in nature and shows absorption maximum at 363–368 nm. The molar absorptivity of the complex is 3.088×10^3 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ with a Beer's law range of 0–15.5 µg mL⁻¹. The method is quite simple and rapid and has been satisfactorily applied for the determination of palladium in µg amounts in various synthetic and technical samples.

Keywords : Palladium, benzildioxime, thiocyanate, spectrophotometry.

In a wide variety of samples, palladium is generally present in very low concentrations. This fact calls for laying out better methods of trace determination, based on specific and sensitive reactions of the metal ion which will go a long way towards its enrichment in the by-products of many industrial processes and use in a large number of alloys with other transition elements and also as a catalyst. Though several mono – as well as dioximes¹ have earlier been employed for complexation of palladium in acid solutions for carrying out determinations after extraction into organic solvents, but the methods still suffer from serious interferences and low sensitivity too. An attempt has, therefore, been made to work out a simple spectrophotometric method using benzildioxime as a complexing agent in presence of thiocyanate with a view to contain these problems to the minimum, with the following details.

Experimental

Apparatus, reagents and solutions : A UV spectrophotometer, 140-02 (Shimadzu, Japan) with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used. A stock solution (1 mg mL⁻¹) of palladium was obtained by dissolving 0.167 g of PdCl₂ (Sisco) in 0.75 mol L⁻¹ HCl and was standardized gravimetrically². Working solutions at the concentration level of µg mL⁻¹ were prepared by suitable dilutions. Similarly, the solutions of other metal ions were obtained by dissolving their commonly available sodium or potassium salt in deionised water or dilute acids. The solution of potassium thiocyanate, 20% (m/v) was prepared by dissolving it in deionised water. Solution of benzildioxime (S.D.'s 'R'), 0.05% (m/v) was prepared by dissolving it in acetone. Hydrochloric acid 2 mol L⁻¹ was used.

Synthetic samples : Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing the solution of various metal ions in suitable proportion, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Analysis of various samples with the proposed method

Matrix ^a	Sample composition	Pd found ^b
	Pd added (µg)	(µg)
V (0 1), Cr (0 1)	100	102 86
W (0 1), U (0 05), Zn (1)	70	72 40
Co (1), Mo (0 1)	50	48 90
Fe (0 01), Se (1), Be (1)	80	78 78
Nb (0 1), Th (0 1), Ru (0 01)	120	117 24
Pt (0 1)	50 ^c	47 80
Re (0 1), Pb (1)	50	47 80
Ni (2)	100	98 55
[Ni (0 04), Pt (0 10), V (0 070)] ^f	120	117 24
Pd-charcoal catalyst (50)	5%	4.78%

^aAmount of the metal ion shown in parentheses is in mg.

^bAverage of triplicate analyses

^cComposition analogous to cooperite

Pd-charcoal catalyst (Aldrich 20,568-0) : The sample (0.05 g) was dissolved in a minimum volume of aqua regia by heating. The charcoal was filtered off when hot. Nitric acid was destroyed completely by evaporating the solution to dryness. The residue thus obtained was dissolved in water, filtered and the filtrate was processed for the determination of palladium as described in the procedure.

To the sample solution containing ≤155 µg of palladium(II) in a 10 mL volumetric flask, 0.5 mL of 2 mol L⁻¹ HCl, 0.2 mL of 20% (m/v) thiocyanate, 0.3 mL of 0.05% (m/v) benzildioxime and the appropriate amount of deionised water were added to make the final volume up to the mark. The absorbance of the complex formed in aqueous phase was measured at 364 nm against the blank prepared analogously. Palladium content was determined from the calibration curve prepared in a similar manner.

Results and discussion

Palladium(II) forms a light yellow colored species with benzildioxime in presence of thiocyanate in acidic medium.

The complex was though stable in aqueous solution but was not found to be extractable in organic solvents. Therefore, all the absorbance measurements were carried out in aqueous phase. Maintaining same acidity (1 mol L^{-1}), the absorbance of the palladium complex was measured in different acids. The absorbance was found to be quite stable in HCl and hence hydrochloric acid medium was preferred.

For achieving maximum absorbance of the complex, the optimum conditions worked out are sample solution containing $\leq 155 \mu\text{g}$ of palladium, requires $0.10\text{--}1.00 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ HCl, $0.2\text{--}0.4 \text{ mL}$ of 20% (m/v) potassium thiocyanate and $0.2\text{--}0.3 \text{ mL}$ of 0.05% (m/v) benzildioxime in acetone in 10 mL aqueous volume whose absorbance is measured at 364 nm .

The absorption spectrum of the Pd^{II} -benzildioxime- SCN^- complex is shown in Fig. 1 with maximum at $363\text{--}368 \text{ nm}$, where the reagent blank has minimal absorbance. Beer's law is obeyed over the palladium concentration range of $0\text{--}15.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. However, the optimum concentration range worked out for the determination of Pd is $2.69\text{--}15.14 \mu\text{g Pd mL}^{-1}$, as evaluated from Ringbom plot. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 364 nm are $3.088 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0345 \mu\text{g Pd cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The ratio of Pd^{II} to benzildioxime and thiocyanate in the aqueous species was found to be $1 : 1 : 2$ by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper³. This was further confirmed by the mole ratio method.

The influence of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the procedure, in 10 mL aqueous volume : chloride, bromide, oxalate, nitrate, acetate, tartrate, carbonate, phosphate and sulfosalicylic acid (50 mg each); sulphate, ascorbic acid, citrate and EDTA 'disodium salt' (30 mg each); iodide, fluoride and sulfite (20 mg each) are without effect. However, nitrite and thiourea show interference. Among of the cations, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and As^{V} (10 mg each); Re^{VII} , Be^{II} and Se^{IV} (5 mg each); Cr^{III} (1.25 mg); Pd^{II} , Cr^{VI} , Zr^{IV} , Nb^{V} , Th^{IV} and Ti^{IV} (1 mg each); Fe^{II} (0.7 mg); Os^{VIII} , V^{V} and Mo^{VI} (0.5 mg each); Ir^{III} , Au^{III} , W^{VI} and Pt^{II} (0.1 mg each); U^{VI} (0.08 mg); Fe^{III} (0.02 mg) and Ru^{III} (0.01 mg) do not show any absorbance. Ag^{I} and Bi^{III} interfere seriously. The interference due to Cu^{II} can be eliminated by using EDTA. For masking copper (0.04 mg), if present in the sample, 30 mg EDTA 'disodium salt' is required to be added before the reagent.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of Pd^{II} - SCN^- -benzildioxime complex (A) $10 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of palladium measured against reagent blank, (B) reagent blank measured against water

Applications : The proposed method for the microdetermination of palladium analyses satisfactorily a wide variety of samples as shown in Table 1. The method is free from the interference of a large number of other elements of analytical interest which are generally found to be associated with the metal ion in natural samples and alloys. The results obtained are quite reproducible with a standard deviation of ± 0.0021 for ten replicate measurements, each time with the same amount of the metal ion. The method compares favourably with the existing methods in terms of selectivity, and rapidity sensitivity⁴.

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